

CHALLENGES OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IMPLEMENTATION IN HEALTHCARE SYSTEMS IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Introduction: Artificial Intelligence (AI) holds immense potential to address critical gaps in healthcare systems, particularly in developing countries. By improving access to specialists, enhancing public health surveillance, and supporting disease management, AI can play a significant role in achieving Universal Health Coverage and Sustainable Development Goals [1]. However, implementing AI in these regions presents several challenges that must be carefully addressed.

Review: Implementing AI in healthcare within low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) faces several significant challenges. One of the primary issues is the quality and availability of data, as AI systems require large, high-quality datasets to function effectively, but many LMICs struggle with incomplete or poorly managed health data [1]. Additionally, there are substantial infrastructure and connectivity barriers, as many regions lack the necessary digital infrastructure to support AI technologies [1]. Privacy, security, and ethical issues present substantial challenges, especially including data ownership, informed consent, and the ethical application of AI in healthcare settings [1, 2]. Furthermore, regulatory and legal frameworks in these countries are often underdeveloped, creating uncertainty and hindering the adoption of AI technologies [2]. Financial constraints and resistance to change among healthcare providers and stakeholders further complicate the integration of AI into healthcare systems [1]. Addressing these challenges requires substantial investments in digital infrastructure, robust regulatory frameworks, and collaborative efforts to build the necessary capacity and trust in AI technologies. Effective cooperation among international organizations, governments, and non-governmental entities is crucial for developing the required infrastructure, educating stakeholders, and setting benchmarks for data generation and AI deployment.

Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) offer significant opportunities in LMICs but also present challenges, such as privacy concerns, interoperability issues, and varying regulations across countries [3]. Overcoming resistance to change requires awareness campaigns, and laws must evolve to accommodate new technologies. Addressing these challenges involves improving data quality, ensuring scalability, and managing algorithmic bias in AI applications.

Conclusion: Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into healthcare systems of low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) has great potential for transformation. However, it encounters major obstacles such as data quality issues, infrastructure deficiencies, and ethical considerations. To overcome these obstacles, it is necessary to make focused investments, establish strong regulatory frameworks, and foster international cooperation to enhance capabilities, guarantee responsible use of AI, and fully capture its advantages for healthcare in developing nations.

Keywords: Review, Artificial Intelligence, Healthcare, Low-and-Middle income countries

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